

THE ART OF UZBEK MUSIC AND ITS FORMATION STAGES

Sobirov Samandar

State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan
Teacher of the "National Singing" department

Abstract: This article describes the two main aspects of the musical heritage of the Uzbek people - musical folklore and professional musical creativity, the composition of main genres, the basis of the grouping of national instruments, the general structure of Shashmaqom, and specific traditions of compositional creativity. Also, information about the role of solo singing in Uzbek music, the stages of its formation, and pedagogical methods of training is given.

Key words: musical art, art forms, opera, symphony, mind, intuition, ability, talent.

Music is an integral part of television, radio, theater, visual arts and all other forms of art, while having a special status among all forms of art. With his impressive nature, he is of incomparable importance in educating the employees of the future field. Means of expression in music (harmony, melody, timbre, dynamic tones, etc.); music genres: vocal, dance, symphonic, chamber, programmed, pictorial; musical-dramatic genres: opera, ballet, operetta, vaudeville, musical; vocal-symphonic genres: oratorio, cantata, messa, requiem; genres of instrumental music: sonata, trio, quartet, quintet, concerto, etc. imply detailed study within the topics allocated to each semester.[1] In this article, the main developmental stages of compositional creativity in the art of music, the life and creative path of classical composers, the classification symbols of opera and symphony genres, the two main musical heritage of the Uzbek people - musical folklore and professional musical creativity, the composition of the main genres, the national instrument Topics such as the basis of their grouping, the general structure of Shashmaqom, and the specific traditions of compositional creativity are described. In this, first of all, musical folklore expressions are studied, and then attention is paid to relatively complex genres (song, big song, status, etc.) and music of the period of independence.[2] Music is a form of social consciousness For a person who begins to study the history of musical art, a long process and continuous rise in the life of music is revealed. When and how was music created? To answer this question, let's turn our attention to the history of mankind. The question remains unanswered.

This is not surprising, because the development of the art of music, like other arts (dance, painting), began to appear gradually. The art of music, dance, and painting turned into art without being noticed for a long time. Because on this path, a person had to find his identity, in this process lies the work enriched by his consciousness, the experiences he has accumulated in his life, and his active connection with the environment that surrounds him. Primitive system of life left a long mark in human history. According to the information of our science, the music culture was left in

the archeological excavations by the primitive man in the pictures. The study of people's life is still in the early stages of development. According to the understanding of our contemporaries, the artistic creation of primitive people was not part of art. Their work was distinguished by independent work. They are organically connected with other vital factors and are subordinated for the purpose of experiment. But from the very beginning, art was associated with the expression of people's feelings. Art draws attention to the beginning of human spirituality: this activity serves not only as a useful experience, but also in the creation of the undiscovered ability and talent of a person, the pursuit of excellence and beauty. The primitive man's view of the world has never left him, it was formed in the feeling of fear. The world surrounding him was full of secret enmity and enmity for him. In order to survive in life, in addition to personal qualities, a person needs strength, endurance, resourcefulness, agility, and understanding.

The biggest support was the behavior attached to him by his descendants, brought up under strict upbringing, the word "taboo" was used, and the experiences he had gained. Such collective manifestations made the mind of a primitive man inevitable.[3] Primitive man knew a lot about birds and animals, trees and grasses, from the flow of rivers to terrible storms. The fact that he uses nature with precision in the depiction of wild animals (Nascal manuscripts, for example: Altamir cave), and perspective with sharpness and dynamism amazes people. But he did not feel or see the inner connection. Because it all seemed fantastic to him. Primitive man firmly believed that objects do not have their own appearance, but have a hidden appearance. Objects were thought to have some mystical powers and to be able to solve problems for life. In his mind there was something real and extraordinary, and there was no limit to it. His thoughts are very different from the people of our time. A person penetrates the essence of things not only with his mind, but with his intuition. They are divided into two: "Generosity seeking good" and "Tendency to evil" which lead to destruction and decay.[4] Music was associated with everyday life. The role of music was aimed at uniting people and inviting them to work together. Battle cries and song-like singing served as a great tool for trapping animals during hunting, while melodious whistling, similar to birdsong, helped hunters catch wild birds. The role of music as such a mediator became the basis for the creation of labor songs in various processes, such as working with the land and farming. But primitive people thought that music is controlled by supernatural forces, and they looked at music as a factor that warded off bad evil forces and brought success to the work started. They believed so much that, for example, if they wore animal skins, sang and danced like animals, they would turn them to their side. They thought that it would bring them luck in the hunt by depicting the pantomime of shooting with an animal and shooting a bow at a doll made of animal skin. Music, dance, pantomime, sacred ceremonies, their vital ordination, all these were an indivisible unity.

The essence of "games" here is to bring joy to the participants and initiate aesthetics. This is how art begins to enter us - syncretically, as a whole. The initial formation of music is related to a different approach to singing. The process of acquiring one's own voice was very long and difficult. From chaotic, Glissandre tones, it gradually transitioned to melodies. Melodies are played with precise pitches. Instrumental music appeared later. New and more modern work tools, musical instruments began to appear in the process of human activity. First of all, percussion instruments appeared. Things that surrounded him in human activities: they also used stone slabs and animal bones. Then wind instruments appeared (reeds, animal mouths).[5] And finally, the strings began to appear. Despite the development of musical instruments, singing was of primary importance. It was here that an important choice was being made, elements of the musical language. Chaos and randomness were replaced by harmony and order. Songs of various labor, war, alla and other genres began to form. Polyphonic songs, choirs (burdon tunes) appeared. Songs enriched with artistic beauty remained in people's memory.

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